

Numerical characterization of a propane-CO₂ refrigeration system developed for TES last-mile delivery

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ABSTRACT

Last-mile delivery represents a key link to preserve the cold chain of temperature-sensitive products during their distribution in urban areas. For this specific application, an increasingly utilized solution are vehicles transporting insulated boxes equipped with eutectic plates, acting as a thermal energy storage (TES), charged before the products distribution activity with a stationary refrigeration unit.

With this purpose, a newly developed stationary refrigeration system is presented, employing the natural refrigerants propane (R290) as operating fluid in the vapour compression cycle and pumped CO₂ (R744) to freeze the eutectic plates mounted in the insulated box, to improve both the energy performance and the environmental sustainability of the application compared to currently employed solutions.

In this study, the dimensioning of the refrigeration system is discussed, and the development of a lumped-parameters numerical model of the unit allows for the preliminary system performance characterization under different operating conditions.

Keywords: Refrigerated transport; Last-mile delivery; Thermal energy storage; Eutectic plates; Propane; Carbon Dioxide; Numerical modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

In latest years, the implementation of thermal energy storage (TES) solutions for refrigeration systems within the food chain, based on the employment of phase change materials (PCMs), which can solidify or melt at a specific temperature level, have gained significant interest, and many research studies and commercial systems have been developed. The aim is to improve flexibility, to avoid delocalised refrigeration units or to promote compliance with renewable energy sources. Transport refrigeration is a key link in the cold chain, however it is one of its most environmentally impactful steps (according to IIR, 2021, refrigerated transport is responsible for about 50 Mt CO_{2,eq}, accounting for nearly 25% of the total cold chain emissions); additionally, new services related to e-commerce and last mile delivery of perishable goods have significantly increased in the post-covid era. For these reasons, a growing interest in the application of TES solutions in transport refrigeration has been experienced.

Extensive reviews regarding the state-of-the-art of the employment of PCMs for temperature-controlled transport and distribution applications along the cold chain can be found in Calati et al. (2022) and in Umate and Sawarkar (2024). The most common research fields regarding the implementation of PCMs in transport refrigeration applications consist of its employment in the insulation walls of refrigerated boxes or containers (Ahmed et al., 2010), or as an integral part of a cooling unit mounted on the vehicle (Liu et al., 2012; Principi et al., 2017) or, mostly, as a TES in eutectic plates mounted in insulated bodies.

Eutectic plates systems have already found application in the market (Calati et al., 2022) and the technology is already reported and regulated by the ATP agreement (United Nations, 2020). Such systems require a stationary cooling unit to freeze the eutectic plates installed inside the insulated body

when the vehicle is parked in the logistics depot, to then exploit the stored energy at low temperature to provide passive refrigeration inside the insulated body during deliveries. In some cases, the refrigerating unit is united to the vehicle or the insulated box itself, but it is only plugged when it is back to the depot.

Although eutectic plates systems can be considered as the most mature alternative to conventional cooling units mounted on refrigerated vehicles, a recent study by Fertel et al. (2023) regarding the refrigerated vehicles fleet currently employed in France showed that only 2.7% of road transport refrigeration systems consists of eutectic plates applications, while the remaining 95.3% still employs active vapour compression systems installed on board of the refrigerated vehicle. In particular, these systems are powered directly by the vehicle prime engine for small sized vans or by a dedicated diesel engine for larger trucks, with low energy efficiency (Tassou et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2012; Minetto et al., 2023).

At the same time, sustainability challenges are exponentially increasing the interest in natural refrigerants (in particular carbon dioxide and hydrocarbons) in newly developed transport refrigeration units.

The objective of this study is the development of a novel, efficient and natural refrigerant based refrigeration system relying on the employment of eutectic plates for passive refrigeration during road last mile delivery in urban areas. The proposed solution is meant to replace a baseline cooling unit employing a synthetic refrigerant (R452A) with a system based only on natural refrigerants (propane and CO₂). By doing so, an improvement of TES last mile delivery refrigeration systems can be achieved both in terms of energy efficiency and long-term environmental sustainability, while still ensuring the correct preservation conditions for quality, freshness and safety of the transported perishable products.

2. THE REFRIGERATION SYSTEMS

This study focuses on a transportable insulated box, equipped with eutectic plates, acting as a thermal energy storage, for the preservation of food products during last mile delivery. The plates are frozen by a stationary refrigeration system.

In this solution, when the pulldown process starts, the refrigerating energy is stored inside the eutectic plates in the form of latent heat of the contained quantity of PCM, which solidifies at a specific temperature level. The stationary cooling unit is then disconnected from the insulated box, which is charged with the food products and then transported by the vehicle for daily deliveries. During this phase, the required temperature for preservation is maintained thanks to the latent energy stored in the eutectic plates, where the PCM progressively melts at fixed temperature level, granting a passive refrigeration effect inside the insulated box without the presence of any active cooling unit mounted on the vehicle. Benefits in terms of weight, noise and local pollution can be gained by such a solution.

In this study, an insulated box characterized by external dimensions equal to 1.70 m × 1.00 m × 1.75 m and an internal volume equal to 1.86 m³ is considered for the application, as depicted in Figure 1. Each of the box walls is made of three layers, corresponding to a 94 mm polyurethane foam layer sandwiched between two 3 mm glassfiber reinforced plastic (GRP) layers, reinforced with wooden and metallic structural components to increase the structure sturdiness. The global heat transfer coefficient of the insulated box, evaluated through steady state experimental tests carried out following the procedure defined in Annex 1 of the ATP agreement (United Nations, 2020), is equal to $K = 0.31 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Three eutectic plates are mounted inside the box and connected in series. Two eutectic plates with external dimensions 985 mm × 690 mm × 53 mm and one eutectic plate with external dimensions 795 mm × 485 mm × 54 mm are installed on the top wall, on the upper part of the side wall and on the lower part of the side wall, respectively. The two bigger plates are charged with 28.48 kg of PCM and the smaller plate is charged with 15.13 kg of PCM. The PCM is characterized by a latent heat of fusion equal

to 242.64 kJ/kg and the phase change occurs at a nominal temperature of -33 °C (FIC, 2023). Therefore, the energy that can be stored by the phase change of the PCM inside the three eutectic plates is 17.5 MJ.

Figure 1 – Insulated box equipped with eutectic plates considered for this study.

The baseline stationary cooling unit currently employed consists of a direct expansion vapor compression unit, whose simplified schematic is presented in Figure 2, based on R452A as the operating fluid. The connection points between the stationary unit and the box are highlighted in yellow in the figure. In this case, the eutectic plates correspond to the evaporator of the cooling unit. The unit operates with fixed compressor speed. A thermostatic expansion valve controls the refrigerant evaporation pressure in order to achieve a fixed 5 K superheat at the compressor suction. The baseline cooling unit is able to deliver a cooling effect equal to 560 W during steady-state operation in nominal operating conditions ($T_{amb} = 30\text{ °C}$ and heat exchanged with a source at -33 °C).

In order to increase the overall sustainability, the system described in Figure 3 is proposed. It consists of a R290 vapor compression unit, and a secondary loop pumping liquid CO₂ (R744) to freeze the eutectic plates. A plate heat exchanger acts as the evaporator of the R290 circuit and as the condenser in the R744 circuit. Such a solution has been developed with the objective of avoiding any flow of the flammable refrigerant R290 inside the confined space of the box and eutectic plates. Moreover, the extremely low temperature level at which the PCM changes its phase allows operating with low-pressure phase change R744 in the secondary loop, which displays extremely good heat transfer characteristic and very low viscosity. Also in this case, the unit operates with fixed speed for both the R290 compressor and the R744 pump, and a thermostatic expansion valve enforces a 5 K superheat at the R290 compressor suction. The proposed indirect cooling unit is able to deliver a cooling effect equal to 630 W during steady-state operation in nominal conditions ($T_{amb} = 30\text{ °C}$ and heat exchanged with a source at -33 °C).

Figure 2 – Direct expansion refrigeration system schematic.

Figure 3 – Indirect expansion refrigeration system schematic.

3. NUMERICAL MODEL DESCRIPTION

The refrigeration system is dynamically modelled employing the multi-physics commercial software Simcenter Amesim 2021. The model is based on a lumped parameters approach, where real components are discretized into elements that are connected to represent the entire system. Each element is governed by nonlinear time-dependent differential equations that involve the state variables. These equations are assembled into a system of differential equations, according to the connection of the elements. The system of differential equations is then integrated over time to obtain the model dynamic.

A fixed displacement compressor model is adopted, where the volumetric, mechanical and isentropic efficiencies are interpolated from the manufacturer data, specific for the R452A and the R290 compressors, as functions of the pressure ratio and the suction pressure.

The fin-and-tube condenser is discretized into $N = 4$ lumped volumes. Each discretized volume is subdivided in three nodes, one referring to the refrigerant flow, one to the state of tube wall and fins and one referring to the state of the air. The geometric characteristics of the heat exchanger, such as surface and mass, are equally distributed in each lumped element. Internal convection between the refrigerant and the internal wall, conduction through wall and fins and external convection between the fins and the outside air are considered.

Each of the three eutectic plates is discretized into $N = 4$ lumped volumes. Each discretized volume considers heat transfer in all four directions around the refrigerant tube, according to the discretization schematic presented in Figure 4. Also in this case, the geometric characteristics are equally distributed. Internal convection between refrigerant and internal tube wall, conduction through the tube wall, conduction through PCM, conduction through plate wall, external convection between plate wall and air inside the insulated box, and radiation between plate wall and box internal walls are considered. The PCM behaviour is described according to the thermophysical properties (density and specific heat of

liquid and solid phases, thermal conductivity, latent heat of fusion and temperature of phase change) declared by the eutectic plates manufacturer (FIC, 2023).

Figure 4 – Discretization schematic of each eutectic plate lumped volume. R: refrigerant; TW: tube wall; PCM: phase change material; PW: plate wall; A: insulated box air; BW: insulated box internal wall.

The plate heat exchanger is discretized into $N = 4$ lumped volumes. Each discretized volume is then sub-divided in three nodes (R290 flow, tube wall, R744 flow). Convection between the operating fluid and the tube wall (for both R290 and R744 sides) and conduction through the tube wall are considered.

The convective heat transfer coefficients are evaluated through empirical correlations, available in the literature. For the refrigerant elements (R452A, R290, R744), the used correlations are Gnielinski correlation for single-phase (Gnielinski, 1976), Shah correlation (Shah, 1979) for two-phase condensation and VDI for horizontal tubes correlation (Steiner and Taborek, 1992) for two-phase boiling. For the air elements in the condenser, Colburn j-factor correlation (McQuiston, 1978) is used. For the air elements exchanging heat with the eutectic plate external surface, flat plate correlations are used: Churchill and Chu (1975) for vertical plate and Lloyd and Moran (1974) for horizontal plate.

The dynamic response evaluation of the insulated box is allowed modelling the box through discretization of the box walls into a series of 7 thermal capacities and 6 thermal resistances. The thermal capacities are evaluated according to the box geometrical data and materials. The thermal resistances are evaluated accounting for the geometry and materials and considering also the thermal bridges corresponding to the doors and to the metallic structural reinforcements to reproduce the global heat transfer coefficient measured in the ATP test ($K = 0.31 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Numerical model validation

The numerical model is globally validated against experimental data of the currently adopted baseline system, to verify the accuracy and the robustness of the numerical modelling approach. For this purpose, the experimental data recorded during the ATP test procedure performed on the currently adopted R452A direct refrigeration system is considered, as defined in Annex 1 of the ATP Regulation (United Nations, 2020).

The test is conducted at constant $T_{amb} = 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($\pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Once the mean inside temperature of the insulated box and the temperature of the eutectic plates are in equilibrium with the environmental temperature, the doors are closed and the cooling unit is turned on. The insulated box is kept closed with the cooling unit in operation for 24 h, to cool down and eventually freeze the PCM contained inside the eutectic plates. After 24 h, the cooling unit is turned off and an internal heating appliance equal to $Q_h = 50 \text{ W}$ is switched on. The test is deemed satisfactory in case the mean temperature measured inside the insulated box is maintained below the limit temperature of $T_{i,threshold} = -20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (class C equipment) for 12 h after switching off the cooling unit.

The numerical model of the system is initialized to thermal equilibrium with the environment ($30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), and the only inputs provided to the model consist of a constant ambient temperature equal to T_{amb} , an external control to switch off the cooling unit after 24 h of operation and a constant heating source inside the insulated box equal to Q_h after the unit switch off. The dynamic variation of the average temperature inside the insulated box along the total 36 h of the considered test, for both ATP experimental test and numerical simulation, and the difference on internal temperature between experimental and numerical are reported in Figure 5.

Figure 5 –ATP test on baseline R452A system: (a) Experimental and numerical average internal air temperature inside the insulated box; (b) internal air temperature difference between experimental and numerical.

The internal temperature difference between experimental and numerical results is assessed to be in a range between $-3.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $+2.0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ throughout the entire test, with an average value equal to $-0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In particular, the results highlight that the numerical model is able to reproduce the experimental system behaviour very accurately in correspondence to the sensible heat exchange of the eutectic plates (hours 0-5 and 17-27), when the PCM is in liquid or solid phase and varies its temperature according to

the provided cooling effect, while during the PCM phase change (hours 5-17 and 27-36) the temperature difference between experimental and numerical results is more accentuated.

The reason behind this outcome lies in the thermophysical properties of the PCM implemented in the numerical model. According to the data reported in the commercial datasheet of the eutectic plates manufacturer, the employed PCM is characterized by a nominal phase change temperature equal to -33°C , regardless of the nature of the phase change (from liquid to solid or from solid to liquid). The experimental results, instead, suggest that the actual PCM solidification occurs at a slightly lower temperature than -33°C (hours 5-17) and that the actual PCM melting occurs at a slightly higher temperature than -33°C (hours 27-36), affecting as a consequence the experimental internal air temperature presented in Figure 5a and leading to the temperature differences reported in Figure 5b. This conclusion based on experimental evidence is in accordance with either scientific literature regarding the PCM hysteresis phenomenon (Klimes et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020) and PCM commercial datasheets by other manufacturers (Rubitherm, 2023).

4.2. Numerical evaluation of the refrigeration system performance

As a first step of evaluation, the theoretical performance of a direct refrigeration system, characterized by the exact same schematic of the baseline system presented in Figure 2 but employing only R290 as an almost drop-in for the R452A refrigerant, is numerically assessed. Compared to the baseline system, only the compressor model is changed from R452A to the R290 one. The same correlations are used for heat transfer and pressure losses. The performance of the R290 system is numerically simulated over the first 24 h of pulldown of the ATP test procedure described in Section 4.1 and then compared to the numerical results of the baseline R452A system in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Performance comparison between baseline R452A direct system and R290 direct system over ATP test pulldown: (a) average temperature inside the box; (b) refrigerating effect; (c) compressor power; (d) COP.

The R290 system presents a better performance compared to the baseline R452A system both in terms of internal temperature inside the insulated box and in terms of energy efficiency. While the improvement on the internal air temperature at the end of the pulldown is modest ($-33.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the R452A system, $-34.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the R290 system) and the energy provided by the cooling unit is almost equal in both cases (57.3 MJ for the R452A system, 57.7 MJ for the R290 system), the compressor power input at low evaporation pressures, during the last part of the pulldown, is considerably lower for the R290 system, improving the system COP. The overall pulldown COP, defined as the ratio between the total cooling energy provided by the unit and the total energy draw of the compressor during the pulldown, is equal to 1.03 for the R452A system and to 1.08 (+4.9%) for the R290 system. Moreover, the numerical simulation allows for the assessment of the refrigerant charge distribution of R290 in some components of the system: 91 g in the condenser coils, 13 g in the liquid separator and 12 g in the refrigerant coils inside the eutectic plates, suggesting that such cooling unit could be realized with a total charge of R290 refrigerant under 150 g. However, this specific application is inherently based on an open system structure since the cooling unit needs to be connected and disconnected from the eutectic plates and these operations might introduce safety challenges related to leakages.

The indirect R290-R744 system proposed in this paper, still based only on natural refrigerants, represents a safer alternative compared to a direct R290 system, as R290 refrigerant is confined in the closed loop of the primary circuit of the cooling unit, while the non-flammable and non-toxic R744 is used to deliver the cooling effect through the open connection with the eutectic plates. Therefore, the performance of the indirect R290-R744 system is numerically simulated over the same first 24 h of pulldown of the ATP test procedure and then compared to the numerical results of the baseline R452A system in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Performance comparison between baseline R452A direct system and R290-R744 indirect system over ATP test pulldown: (a) average temperature inside the box; (b) refrigerating effect; (c) compressor power; (d) COP.

The indirect R290-R744 system presents a slightly different behaviour compared to the baseline R452A system. Firstly, the internal air temperature at the end of the pulldown is considerably higher in the R290-R744 system (-29.3 °C) than in the R452A system (-33.5 °C). Despite that, the total energy provided by the cooling unit does not present such a remarkable difference (57.3 MJ for the R452A system, 55.7 MJ for the R290-R744 system, -2.8%).

The main reason behind this resides in the different heat exchange in the eutectic plates between the two systems. Figure 8 presents the normalized latent energy stored in the three plates in the R452A and in the R290-R744 systems. In the baseline R452A system, the thermostatic expansion valve fixing the 5 K superheat at compressor suction is placed after the outlet of the plates. Since the eutectic plates are connected in series, the first plates operate with evaporating refrigerant, therefore achieving high heat transfer coefficients, and with lower temperature, suitable for plate freezing, while the last plate operates within the superheated state of the refrigerant, therefore with lower heat transfer coefficients and higher temperature. As a consequence, the first two plates allow for early PCM solidification and even further subcooling while the last plate only partially freezes, while the subcooling of the other plates cools down the air inside the box.

Instead, in the R290-R744 system, two-phase R744 guarantees constant temperature in all three eutectic plates, leading to the simultaneous solidification of the PCM in all three plates and to an even distribution of the cooling effect (consistently with the plates sizes). In such operating conditions, the refrigerant temperature inside the plates is maintained the same until all the PCM is solidified and, as a consequence, the air temperature inside the insulated box remains at a higher level than in the baseline system. Overall, approximately the same total amount of cooling energy is stored in the three eutectic plates, but distributed differently. In the R290-R744 system, the TES is in the form of full latent heat in all three plates, while in the baseline system the TES is in the form of latent and sensible heat in the first plates and only partial latent heat in the last plate.

Figure 8 – Normalized latent heat stored in the eutectic plates: (a) baseline R452A system; (b) indirect R290-R744 system.

The overall pulldown COP over the 24 h operation of the proposed indirect R290-R744 system is equal to 1.07, corresponding to a +3.9% increase compared to the baseline R452A system and almost identical to the direct R290 system.

4.3. Influence of different ambient temperature

To assess the influence of different operating conditions on the performance of the proposed R290-R744 system and compare it with the baseline R452A system, numerical simulations from initial thermal equilibrium with the environment at different ambient temperatures are carried out. To ensure a fair comparison between the two systems, pulldown COPs are evaluated considering the pulldown completed when a fixed amount energy is stored into the plates. This reference energy is assumed equal to the heat required to cool down the total PCM mass from ambient temperature to the phase

change temperature (-33 °C) and then completely freeze the plates. The results are presented in Figure 9 for ambient temperature equal to 20 °C, 30 °C and 40 °C. It needs to be highlighted that the pulldown COPs presented in Figure 9 are different from the ones reported at the end of Section 4.2, since in this case the evaluation is carried out for a fixed amount of cooling energy provided by the units, while in Section 4.2 the evaluation considers a fixed pulldown time.

Figure 9 – Influence of ambient temperature on the pulldown COP of the baseline R452A and proposed R290-R744 systems performance.

For $T_{amb} = 20$ °C, the proposed system delivers the target amount of cooling energy presenting a pulldown COP equal to 1.45, with a slightly higher efficiency compared to the baseline system (1.43). For $T_{amb} = 30$ °C, the energy performance is the same for the two systems (pulldown COP equal to 1.14 in both cases). For $T_{amb} = 40$ °C, the R290-R744 system presents a slightly lower pulldown COP (0.75) than the baseline system (0.88). The reason for such behaviour resides in the longer time required by the proposed system to provide the target amount of cooling energy, as the cumulative effect of convection and radiation on the eutectic plates over time influence the overall system energy performance. An increase of the nominal capacity of the R290-R744 system will reduce the pulldown time and consequently increase the pulldown COP.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a novel indirect refrigeration system employing the natural refrigerants propane (R290) and CO₂ (R744) is proposed as an energy efficient and environmentally sustainable solution to serve transport refrigeration and last mile delivery applications based on eutectic plates charged with PCM and installed inside an insulated box. The proposed system is meant to replace a baseline system employing the synthetic refrigerant R452A, directly expanding inside the plates.

A dynamic numerical model of the baseline and of the proposed refrigeration systems is developed and validated against experimental data collected during the ATP test procedure carried out on the baseline system, showing good accordance. The main discrepancies between the experimental data and the numerical model results are due to the lack of an accurate description of the thermophysical properties of the PCM charged inside the used eutectic plates.

The performance of the proposed system is then numerically simulated in the same ATP pulldown conditions (with ambient temperature equal to 30 °C) and then compared to the baseline system performance. The two systems present a different evolution of the internal air temperature during the pulldown, with the R290-R744 system leading to a higher internal temperature at the end of the pulldown (-29.3 °C instead of -33.5 °C), despite an almost equal (-2.8%) cooling energy subtracted from the eutectic plates. The different system architecture leads to different operating conditions in the eutectic plates, with the R290-R744 system fully exploiting the latent heat of solidification of the PCM.

With ambient temperature equal to 30 °C, the overall pulldown COP over the 24 h operation of the proposed system is equal to 1.07, with an increase of + 3.9% compared to the baseline R452A system.

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